

Energy Modelling for Rwanda: Integrating Solar and Large-Scale Battery Storage to Address Excessive Peak Demand

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Executive Summary

Using the OSeMOSYS tool, three scenarios were modeled to assess Rwanda's energy future. The Business As Usual (BAU) scenario indicates a continued heavy reliance on non-renewable energy sources, resulting in significant CO₂ emissions throughout the modeling period. Scenario Two introduces renewable energy sources, with a particular emphasis on solar energy, leading to a substantial reduction in emissions. Building upon this, Scenario Three incorporates battery storage systems and phases out diesel-based power generation, achieving the most significant CO₂ emissions reduction among the scenarios. Therefore, Scenario Three is highly recommended for the Government of Rwanda to consider in its strategic energy planning.

1. Introduction

Rwanda, through Rwanda Energy Group (REG), currently has a total installed generation capacity of 406.4 MW and projects to reach 1,066 MW or more by 2034 in response to growing demand. This power is generated from five main sources: hydropower, methane gas, peat-fired power plants, imports, shared power, thermal power, and solar energy. Hydropower is the largest contributor, accounting for 27.0% of the installed capacity, while solar energy contributes the least at 3.0% (REG Annual reports-FY 2023/24).

In its forecasts, REG aims for renewable energy sources to contribute up to 60% of the total generation capacity by 2034. Given Rwanda's strong solar energy potential, solar is expected to be a key contributor to this target.

The surge in peak demand, which mainly occurs between 6 PM and 11 PM, often requires the operation of non-renewable power plants such as thermal plants. To address

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this challenge, battery storage systems are identified as a key solution, with REG recognizing a significant need for such systems in these scenarios.

Three scenarios are modeled using OSeMOSYS: the business-as-usual case based on historical data and resource availability; a scenario emphasizing solar energy integration; and another incorporating battery storage to supply power during peak hours.

2. Methodology

The Modeling User Interface for OSeMOSYS (MUI-O) is a specialized tool for energy capacity expansion planning to meet the demand. It optimizes future energy trends based on available resources and aligns with existing policies, supporting effective energy planning.

The data used in this modelling process draws from various strategic documents, studies, and platforms. These include the Least Cost Power Development Plan, Rwanda Energy Group annual reports, Strategic Energy Planning documents, the Rwanda Resource Study on electricity generation sources (EAEP, May 2022), the Africa Energy Commission (AFREC) platform, and the study on enabling energy frameworks for electric mobility in Rwanda, among others.

The historical calibration period spans from 2021 to 2023. For the modeling period from 2021 to 2050, a 3% annual demand growth rate is applied to project future energy demand. Energy resource optimization was carried out to meet this projected demand. During the calibration years, the model referenced the available power plants, as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Rwanda installed power capacity mix

Rwanda's energy supply comes from a diverse mix of sources. In terms of electricity generation, hydropower, natural gas (methane gas), and coal currently dominate the

energy mix. Although Rwanda has significant potential for solar energy, it still contributes a relatively small share to the total installed capacity. Figure 1 below illustrates the Rwanda Reference Energy System, which was modeled using the OSeMOSYS tool.

Figure 2: Rwanda reference Energy System

In our case, we modelled three scenarios:

Business As Usual (BAU): This scenario is based on the historical energy supply trends from 2021 to 2023 and projects an optimized energy pathway through to 2050.

Scenario two: This scenario reflects the integration of government initiatives aimed at expanding renewable energy, with a particular focus on increasing investment in the country's vast solar energy potential. This shift is expected to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions.

Scenario three: In response to the rising peak electricity demand, this scenario introduces battery storage systems and phases out thermal (diesel) power plants. It builds upon Scenario Two by continuing the integration of other renewable energy sources alongside enhanced storage capacity.

3. Results and discussion

Rwanda is experiencing a rapid increase in energy demand, driven by the government's proactive approach to attracting investment in the energy sector. This growth underscores the necessity for strategic and actionable energy system planning. Figure 3 illustrates Rwanda's projected energy production by technology across three modeled scenarios.

In the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario, the energy mix continues to rely heavily on fossil fuels, with diesel, natural gas, and coal power plants contributing the largest share throughout the modeling period. Scenario Two builds upon the BAU scenario by integrating government initiatives aimed at expanding renewable energy sources. Notably, it includes plans to introduce a nuclear power plant by 2034 and significant investments in solar energy starting from 2030. Scenario Three expands on Scenario Two by incorporating battery storage systems from 2030 to address peak demand challenges. It also outlines a gradual reduction in reliance on diesel power plants starting from 2035, culminating in their complete phase-out by 2040.

Figure 3: Production by technology

Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the accumulated new capacity and annualized investment costs across the modeled scenarios. The demand being the same across all of the scenarios, they reveal an increasing capacity and investment cost. With investment costs in Scenarios Two and Three rising by 58% and 67%, respectively, relative to the BAU scenario in 2050, this highlights the need for decision-makers to consider additional benefits such as CO₂ emissions reductions.

It is observed that the increase of renewable energy source leads to the higher investment cost.

Figure 4: Accumulated new capacity

Figure 5: Annualized investment cost

Due to its continued reliance on non-renewable energy sources, the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario projects high CO₂ emissions throughout the modeling period. In contrast, Scenario Two incorporates renewable energy sources starting in 2028, leading to a substantial reduction in emissions. Further improvements are observed in Scenario Three from 2037, primarily due to the gradual decrease in diesel-based power generation and the integration of battery storage systems. Figure 5 below illustrates the

CO₂ emissions trends during the modeling period for the three scenarios.

Figure 6: Annual technology emissions

The modelling process revealed most important technologies to be explored in the Rwanda. For instance, though there is no wind generation as of now in the Rwanda energy generation mix; the model suggests the use of wind energy due to its potentiality in the country.

The modeling process faced significant challenges due to limited access to accurate and comprehensive data. This underscores the need for enhanced data collection efforts and the integration of emerging technologies such as nuclear power, battery storage, and wind energy that are not yet part of Rwanda's current energy mix.

7. Conclusion

Rwanda's geographical location offers substantial solar energy potential, presenting a valuable opportunity to boost clean energy production. Currently, non-renewable sources such as diesel power plants are primarily used during peak demand periods. Integrating energy storage technologies particularly large-scale battery systems into the national grid is therefore essential. This integration can significantly reduce dependence on fossil fuels and lower CO₂ emissions. For example, under Scenario Two and Scenario Three, emissions are reduced by 90% and 94%, respectively, compared to business-as-usual (BAU) projections. Given its greater impact on emissions reduction, Scenario Three should be prioritized by policymakers.

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